

Linguistic Investigation of Verbal Abuse and Normal Argument in English Movies: A Comparative Study

Hanan Abdalkareem Kadhim ✉

College of Education, English Department, Al-Farabidi University, Iraq

Maram Salam Abdul Kareem

Al-Aqeeda High School, Ministry of Education, Bagdad, Iraq

Nahid Raoof Kareem

Al-Nabugh Secondary School, Ministry of Education, Bagdad, Iraq

Abstract

This study aims at investigating how men and women are different in their ways of argument whether in normal one or in using verbal aggression. This is done by analyzing two characters from two movies. The first movie is "Revolutionary Road" and the second one is "My Fault". The researchers intended to use an eclectic model which includes Verbally abusive relationship by Evans (2009), Searle's (1969) speech act theory of, Brown and Levenson's (1978) politeness theory and Culpeper's (1996) impoliteness theory. The results are that men used abusive anger and name-calling with positive and negative impoliteness as forms of violence while women use judging and criticizing with bald on record and positive impoliteness as a form of violence. It is also found out that the men use representative speech act in normal argument while women use directive speech act but both of them used bald on record and negative politeness.

Keywords: *verbal abuse, normal argument, speech acts.*

Suggested citation: Kadhim, H.A., Kareem, M.S.A., & Kareem, N.R. (2025). Linguistic Investigation of Verbal Abuse and Normal Argument in English Movies: A Comparative Study. *European Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(6), 40-55. DOI: 10.59324/ejahss.2025.2(6).05

Introduction

Communication is a process of sending and receiving information, ideas and emotions from the sender or the speaker to the listener or receiver. This process is complex since it involves a message that has different meanings decoded differently. The speech is a way of practicing this process. Hate speech is one of the hardest speeches since determining it is very linguistically nuanced. In other words, the view of linguistic action is in contrast with a tradition of speech-act theory (Austin, 1962; Searle, 1969) in which the meaning of an utterance is not solely determined by lexical or syntactic structure but by its social context and performativity effects. Butler (1997) sees that words are seen not just as arbitrary lexemes but something capable of actively causing violence to one or more addressees. Butler, in her account of hate speech, optimistically saw a 'gap' between a speech act and its effects (Butler, 1997) comparably to Austin's distinction between the illocutionary (the addressee's intention) and perlocutionary (the outcome of the utterance). She argues against legal regulation of hate speech attributing the 'restaging' and 'signifying' such speech on the part of the addressee. Schwartzman (2002), however claimed that Butler's account was fundamentally uncompleted because it missed an awareness of existing social structures of power.

Research Questions

1. What is the verbal abusive tool and impoliteness strategy used by the men and women?

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/). The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

2. What is speech act category and politeness strategy used by the men and the women in normal argument?

The researchers intend to answer these questions through analyzing a man and a woman from two movies displayed in the fifties. The method of analysis is an eclectic model consist of Evan's verbal abuse relationship (2009), Searls speech act theory (1969), Brown and Levienson politeness theory (1978) and Culpeper impoliteness theory (1996).

Theoretical Background

Verbal Abuse and Normal Argument

Marteney J. (n. d) and Hitchcock (2007) defined an argument similarly as a complex structure consists of two speech acts, premises and conclusion. This part of communication happens to resolve an actual disagreement, confusion, or ignorance between interlocutors about something. The conclusion depends on how the participants present the premises as truth to persuade the listener of a certain opinion o on an issue. This needs skilled participants and follow the reason to argue constructively. Abusive language is defined variously by different scholars. Battistella (2005) defined it as a language that does not follow the rules. O'Driscoll (2020, p.16) refers to it as "any word or string of words which has or can have a negative impact on the sense of self and/or wellbeing of those who encounter it. In other words, a group of words that gives bad feel on the part of the listener. Stollznow (2020, p. 2) says it is "something said to us that we find to be morally repulsive or personally insulting. It is a language that strikes the core of our beliefs or identity and affects us on a fundamental level "The key distinction between argument and abusive language is that how heated exchanges among speakers occur and the nature of these exchanges. Arguments are typically isolated disagreement about certain ideas and opinions on certain claim from the relationship among speakers avoiding damaging these relationships. This isolation is recognized by trying to reach to a resolution using apologies for disagreement (shadows of control (2024). The expert John Gottman claims that healthy conflicts involve a willingness to understand the perspective of the other side finding a common ground (Gottman & Silver, 1999). Such disagreements are temporary and focused on specific issues, without damaging the relationship's foundation. In using abusive language, the intention is to attack verbally in order to control and belittle the other entity. That means the speaker addresses the personality of the speaker not his behavior and idea. To sum up, in normal argument, both partners try to reach to a shared point of conversation while in using abusive language, one entity tries to enforce the other one to accept his own idea without any persuasion. Argument is conflict while verbal abuse is violation.

Previous Studies

There are very few studies that conducted the violence. These studies are:

Tartory, Khoury, Tayyeb, Al-Qudah, and Al Akash, (2022). They investigate verbal violence in literature particularly reveal the structure abusers use and the effect that verbal abuses have on their victims. They analyzed 'Merchant of Venice' written by William Shakespeare. It is found out that the most verbal abuse forms occurred in the text are Judging and criticizing, Trivializing, Undermining, Threatening, Name-calling and Abusive anger.

Diani, Arono, and Yunita (2022) observed the verbal abuse in language against women and children on social media, at schools, and in families by Bengkulu communities in the coastal areas of the Bengkulu province. Using Cresswell (2017), they analyzed 35 informants that spread on social media, at schools, and in families with a purposive sampling technique in in three stages: data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing. The main results revealed the verbal abuses occurred in the form of disrespectful words, bullying, cyberbullying, words that are considered demeaning, insulting, intimidating, blasphemous, homophobic, sarcastic, yelling, cursing, ridiculing, yelling, slander, harsh words, scolding, and nagging excessively, cold, and humiliating in public.

Yousif (2023) conducted a descriptive method to describe the language of insult as it is used by some English news media, namely, ITV News and BBC News. This study is conducted by performing a socio-pragmatic analysis based on some contexts of English news. This study gives a BBC model of insulting language that reveals moments of highly emotional reality. The main findings are the use of insult words sometimes embodies a sense of personal hatred as in 'gleeful', the reflect racial content as in 'nigger' and the use of some positive words leads to an offense as in 'wheelchair bound'.

Hugh Klein, and Shiffman (2012) examines the types of messages provided by verbal aggression. Relying upon the analysis of the content of an animated cartoon as a type medium to which young people are exposed at early age, the main results reveal that verbal aggression is fairly prevalent in cartoons (it is the second most common type of antisocial behavior shown, ranking second only to violence) and that this prevalence has increased greatly over time.

It is observed that these studies used different ways of analyzing verbal abuse. Only one of them used Practica Evan's model (2009) in literature. The other studies shaded light on different context but none of them investigated the violence forms used by man and women. The current study intends to reveal this side in communication and compare it with the acts used by different genders in normal argument.

The Models of Study

Practica Evan (2009)

In her book "*The Verbally Abusive Relationship*" Evan claims that verbal abuse is a form of violence that has emotional wounds not like physical violence which has bodily scars. She classified the types of this kind of violence into fifteen types:

1. Withholding: means adding or sharing unneeded information to the current occasion or adding this information haphazardly.
2. Countering: means ending the conversation by giving different opinion that disagree with the other participant.
3. Discounting: means denying the victims opinion and making him or her feels that it is unimportant through criticizing his participation in communication.
4. Verbal abuse disguised as jokes: means that the abuser intends to humiliate the victim through making jokes on his opinion hiding his insulting.
5. Blocking and diverting: means stop discussing the reasonable subject going far away from it. It also includes changing the conversation topic.
6. Accusing and blaming: means blaming and accusing the victim for things that are nothing or not done like blaming of cheating on him or her.
7. Judging and criticizing: means using judgmental evaluation that effect on the victim's self-worth.
8. Trivializing: means minimizing what the victim says or does through commenting negatively.
9. Undermining: means minimizing what the victim says or does but in a deeper way. he intends to what the victim is proud of.
10. Threatening: it is a direct way of controlling the victim's behavior through potential, physical or sexual violence.
11. Name calling: means calling negative names explicitly or implicitly. like stupid or you're just so perfect, aren't you.
12. Forgetting: mean forgetting the interaction and discussing about an important object for the victim as a way of manipulation
13. Ordering: it is another type of direct control by getting the victim to do undesired thing.
14. Denial: means justifying the indirect disagreeing with what is said or done by the victim.
15. 15. Abusive anger means yelling, shouting or screaming combined sometimes with insulting insults, swearing and breaking things.

Searl's speech act theory (1969)

It is an updating theory of Speech act that was proposed by Austin in 1962. He involves performing actions through utterances. He classified speech into five kinds:

1. *Assertive speech act*

Assertive is a kind of speech act that includes the belief of the speaker. In an assertive speech act, someone can tell people how things are. In other words, the speaker presents a proposition according to his or her understanding Searle (1985). These acts like stating concluding, suggesting, boasting, claiming and assuming.

2. *Directive speech act*

Directive is a type of speech act that means getting the receiver of the message to do something These acts like orders, requests and commands. These acts like asking, commanding, requesting, ordering, permitting, begging.

3. *Commissive speech act*

A kind of speech act that means committing the speaker to do something in the future. These acts like plans, threats, pledges, guarantees, and contracts.

4. *Expressive speech act*

Expressive is another kind of speech which means expressing the feelings of the speakers. These acts like speech act like apologizing, thanking, congratulating, praising, and complementing.

5. *Declarative speech act*

A kind of speech acts that means uttering about a certain state leading to changing the current condition or situation to another one. These acts like name, decide, declare pronounce, as Peraica (1987) listed some of them.

Brown and Levenson politeness theory (1978)

Brown and Levinson (1987) link politeness to the nature of face dividing face into positive and negative ones. According to them, positive face is desire of the person to be gracious show shared goals and interests. While negative face is the desire of the person to be free from imposition. These faces can be threatened. So, these scholars proposed to minimize this threat through the following methods are:

1. *Bald on record politeness*

This strategy involves a direct way of saying things, without any minimization to the imposition, in a direct, clear, unambiguous and concise way. This strategy like imperatives which can be implied through hedge to minimize the threat of face.

2. *Positive politeness*

The strategy involves minimizing the difference between the members of certain social groups like friends and family. it includes that there is no correction to the violation of a particular face since this is done by meeting the desires of the participants of that group which is minimizing the difference and sharing the interests among them.

3. *Negative Politeness*

This strategy involves distances between participants. It is used among speakers of different ranks. As they say, it occurs among speakers who want to put social brake in the interaction.

4. *Off record*

Brown and Levinson (1978) defined it as a strategy in which the communicative action cannot be attributed and depend on the interpretation of the listener. He listed some of these strategies like giving

hints, giving association clues, presupposing, understating, overstating, using tautologies, using contradictions, being ironic, using metaphors, and using rhetorical questions.

Culpeper impoliteness theory (1996)

A theory was introduced by Jonathan Culpeper in (1996). It is based on brown and levinson's politeness theory intending to produce a conflict and disharmony between the communication participants in certain discourse Walaszewska and Piskorska (2012). He added a view that politeness is understood and based on impoliteness Mullany and Stockwell (2010). He identified four impolite strategies:

1. Bald on Record Impoliteness

A strategy that is used when the speaker intends deliberately to damage the hearer's face, particularly positive face using impolite utterance (Bousfield, 2008).

In (2005), Culpeper adds a range of sub-strategies to positive impoliteness including (cited in Mullany and Stockwell, 2010):

- neglecting the other
- searching for four different common grounds with the hearer
- choosing an undesirable topic to talk about
- describing the hearer with inappropriate adjectives
- don't appear interested and sympathetic with the hearer
- Looking for disagreements
- Using obscure language and inserting secretive words within the discourse.
- Using taboo words

2. Negative Impoliteness

A strategy that is used when the speaker intends deliberately to damage the hearers face, particularly the negative one (Thielemann and Kosta, 2013). In (2005) he involves the following sub-strategies (cited in Mullany and Stockwell, 2010: 72):

- Scorn
- Frighten
- Ridicule
- Invade the hearer's space literally or metaphorically

3. Sarcasm or Mock Impoliteness (off record)

A strategy that is used when the speaker intends to damage the hearers face indirectly through using utterances that are superficially suitable and accepted but deeply, they have the opposite meaning (Bousfield, 2008).

Methodology

This study focuses on investigating the verbal abuse categories and speech acts used by men and women in normal argument. Particularly, the categories used in two movies "The Revolutionary Road" and "My Fault". For this purpose, an eclectic model is adopted to analyze extracts taken from a man and a woman from each movie. This model consists of the verbal abuse forms of Evans (2009), Brown and Levinson (1978), theory of politeness, Searl's speech act theory (1969) and Culpeper's impoliteness theory (1996).

This study is a mixed research design, qualitative and quantitative method. It involved ten extracts from Frank and April characters in the first movie and Nick and Noah in the second. These movies are

downloaded from Cinemania application. Five extracts analyzed as abusive language and the other five analyzed as normal argument. Then, these extracts are analyzed according to the politeness and impoliteness theories. The results are analyzed qualitatively. The method of this study is summarized in the following diagram:

Figure 1. Evan 's verbal abuse (2009)

Figure 2. Brown and Levionson (1978) politeness theory

Figure 3. Searl's speech act theory (1969)

Figure 4. Culpeper impoliteness theory (1996)

Results

The Forms of Verbal Abuse used by Frank, April, Nick and Noah

Table 1. The Verbal Abuse Techniques and Impoliteness Categories Used by Frank

The extract of the first character (Frank)	The verbal abuse tool	Impoliteness category
1-Frank: Well... I guess it wasn't a triumph or anything, was it?	trivializing	Positive impoliteness (Being disinterested and unsympathetic with the hearer)
2- Frank: Don't you think that's a little bit rude, April?	Name-calling	Positive impoliteness (taboo words)
3- Frank: You're sick. I really mean that. You're sick!	Name-calling	Positive politeness (Using inappropriate identity markers)
4- Frank: I think you're the most interesting person I've ever met.	Judging and criticizing	off record Sarcasm or Mock Impoliteness (off-record)
5- Frank: How about some fresh air, John?	Blocking and diverting	Positive impoliteness Selecting a sensitive or undesirable topic to talk about

Table 2. The Frequencies and Percentages of Verbal Abuse Techniques and Impoliteness Categories Used by Frank

Abusive technique	Frequency	Percentage	Impoliteness strategy	frequency	percentage
Name -calling	2	%40	Positive impoliteness	4	80%
Judging and criticizing	1	20%	Off-record	1	20%
trivializing	1	20%			
Blocking and diverting	1	20%			

Frank uses name calling as a way of control and change the desire of April in leaving the city to Paris. This is clear in his extracts " Don't you think that's a little bit rude, April?" and " You're sick. I really mean that. You're sick!" He also uses positive impoliteness in the former extract through using the taboo word " rude". In the latter extract, he uses inappropriate identity markers as a way of expressing impoliteness through using the expression "you are sick". In his extract " I think you're the most interesting person I've ever met.", he tries to give a judgment upon her personality as a way of enforcing her to change her mind. From impoliteness point of view, he tries to mock her through describing her positively but in reality, he criticizes her. In the extract "Well... I guess it wasn't a triumph or anything, was it?" he uses the expression "triumph" trying to belittle her action and her trying to change the current situation. In these extracts he also positive impoliteness through displaying that he is not interested in her discussion and disagree with her opinion. In the last extract " How about some fresh air, John? He tries to change the topic of discussion as a way of disagree with her opinion and refusing it. At the same time, he uses "having fresh air " is irrelevant to the current discussion is analyzed as positive impoliteness through the strategy choosing undesirable topic.

Statistically, it is clear that Frank used name calling more than other verbal abuse techniques since their percentages are 40,20,20,20 % respectively. This clarifies as Basta (2020) claimed that Frank tried to practice his masculinity and control his wife April. He has an inner conflict between his desire of being seen as a gentleman and his mentality of a man from fifties. He tries to do what his beloved and wife April wants and fulfill her desire of finding happiness and breaking routines. At the same time, he acts as man from fifties who has a power over his wife and children. He also used positive impoliteness and off record mostly since the percentages are 80 and 20% respectively. This means that he used different ways of violating to prevent her from practicing her control on him. He used all kinds of impolite expression to achieve his desire and deliver his idea of refusing.

Table 3. The Speech Act and Politeness Categories Used by Frank

Normal argument	Speech act category	Politeness category
1-Frank: I mean it, baby. You were the only person in that play.	Representative	Positive politeness
2-Frank: Sure. I just don't want you feeling bad about it, that's all. Because it's not worth it. I mean, it's bad enough having to live out here among these damn people -what'd you say?	Representative	Negative politeness
3-Frank: Look, can't we sit in the car and talk about it, instead of running all over Route Twelve?	Directive	Off record
4-Frank: Oh, right, sorry. I thought I'd taken care of that...	Commissive	Bold on record
5-Frank: I hope you weren't planning on an early lunch.	Expressive	Negative politeness

Table 4. The Frequencies and Percentages of Speech Act and Politeness Categories Used by Frank

Speech act category	Frequency	Percentage	Politeness category	Frequency	Percentage
representative	2	40%	Negative politeness	2	40%
Directive	1	20%	Positive politeness	1	20%
commissive	1	20%	Bald on record	1	20%
expressive	1	20%	Off-record	1	20%

In his normal argument, Frank, in his extract "I mean it, baby. You were the only person in that play.", tries to display a fact of her pregnancy to make her change her mind about leaving to Paris. This is clear when he used the verb "mean" and the verb to be "were". He intends that in the past her desire is possible but with the new event it is impossible. From the point of view of speech act theory, he used representatives' speech act while from the point of view of politeness theory he used positive politeness when he used "baby" as a way to mitigate her face threatening act and repair her desire of being acceptable. He also used representative speech act expressing his opinion about the reason behind his desire to stay in the current city. He used "damn people" trying to depict a bad image about the living in Paris. In this time, he used negative politeness that is clear from "what do you say" trying to repair her desire of being free from restricting. It is worth to mention that he expresses in the extract "I hope you weren't planning on an early lunch." his personal desire of staying in the current city through the word "hope" but he tried also to mitigate her desire of being free from restricting through the expression "you weren't planning". In his extract "Look, can't we sit in the car and talk about it, instead of running all over Route Twelve?" he tried to give her an order to sit down in the car changing the place of discussion. This is clear from using "look". This is called direct speech act. He also tried to enforce her to change her mind indirectly through using "can't you". He gives a promise about the future life if she backtracks her decision about leaving to Paris. This is clear in his extract "Oh, right, sorry. I thought I'd taken care of that..." especially in "I would take care". He clearly confesses that he was the reason behind her desire of leaving to Paris through the word "sorry"

Statistically in his normal argument Frank used representative speech act more than other kinds since their frequencies are 40,20,20,20 %. This clarifies that he tried to present claims to prove that his idea is right. He tried to convince April to backtrack about her desire to leave to Paris. One of these claims is that he mentioned her pregnancy as in "I mean it, baby. You were the only person in that play". On the other hand, he used negative politeness mostly since the percentages are 40,20,20,20% respectively. This explains that he tried to make her convince indirectly and change her decision about leaving to Paris. He did this through remedying her negative face of being free and unimpeded. It is also a sign of his desire to make her feel that they are partners in everything minimizing the distance between their ideas and desires.

Table 5. The Verbal Abuse Techniques and Impoliteness Categories Used by April

The second extract (April)	The verbal abuse technique	Impoliteness category
1-April: I think you're the most interesting person I've ever met.	Judging and criticizing	Sarcasm or off record
2-April: I've never really been anywhere	Withholding	Bald on record
3-April: I think it's unrealistic for a man with a fine mind to go on working like a dog year after year at a job he can't stand, coming home to a place he can't stand, to a wife who's equally unable to stand the same things.	Name-calling	Positive impoliteness (taboo words)
4-April: You were not! How can you even say that?	Judging and criticizing	Bald on record
5-April: Well, I don't feel like explaining everything fifteen times to somebody who's too bored and silly to listen!	Judging and criticizing	Positive impoliteness (taboo words)

Table 6. The Frequencies and Percentages of Verbal Abuse Techniques and Impoliteness Categories Used by April

Abusive technique	frequency	percentage	Positive impoliteness	frequency	percentage
Judging and criticizing	3	%60	Bald on record	2	%40
withholding	1	20%	Positive impoliteness	2	40%
Name-calling	1	20%	Off record	1	20%

Qualitatively, April used Judging and criticizing as a way of expressing her violence toward the preventing of frank from achieving herself. this is clear in the following extracts: " I think you're the most interesting person I've ever met.", "You were not! How can you even say that?" and " Well, I don't feel like explaining everything fifteen times to somebody who's too bored and silly to listen!". In these extracts she tried to describe his personality. from politeness point of view, she tried to use different ways of impoliteness. In the first one she described him positively but she intends that he is opposite.in the second one she directly described his personality without any mitigating to his threatening act. In the third one, she used taboo words "bored" and silly" as a way of damaging his desire to be accepted.

On the other hand, she rarely used withholding and name-calling as a verbal abuse. In the extract " I've never really been anywhere" she tried to change the subject of discussion intending to deliver a message of her rejection his preventing. At the same time, she tried to attack deliberately .in the extract " I think it's unrealistic for a man with a fine mind to go on working like a dog year after year at a job he can't stand, coming home to a place he can't stand, to a wife who's equally unable to stand the same things. "She used "dog" trying to belittle his point of view as a way of expressing verbal abuse. From politeness point of view, she used impoliteness technique through using taboo word like "dog".

Quantitatively, April used judging and criticizing as a verbal abuse technique more than the others since their frequencies are 60,20,20 % respectively. This refers to that April is an ideal and wisdom woman. that refers she criticizes the current situation of being just a mother taking care of her husband and children without having any right to achieve her dreams. She also used positive politeness equally to bald on record more than off record since their percentages are 40 ,40 ,20 % respectively. this means that she attacked him by describing his personality differently. This is done either directly through using taboo words or indirectly through giving negative answer to his request.

Table 7. The Speech Act and Politeness Categories Used by April

The extract (April)	Normal argument	Politeness category
1-April: Enough to live on for six months without you earning another dime. And with the money we could get from the house and the car, longer.	representative	Bald on record
2-April: You know how much money we have saved...?	Directive	Negative politeness
3-April: No. Just let me stand here a second.	Directive	Negative politeness
4-April: What are you doing? Why are we stopping?	Directive	Bald on record
5-April: How kind of you. How terribly, terribly kind of you.	Expressive	Positive politeness

Table 8. The Frequencies and Percentages of Speech Act and Politeness Categories Used by April

Speech act category	frequency	percentage	Politeness category	frequency	percentage
Directive	3	60%	Negative politeness	2	40%
expressive	1	20%	Bald on record	2	40%
representative	1	20%	Positive politeness	1	20%

Qualitatively, April used directive in the extract "You know how much money we have saved...? "Focuses on the money they have that is enough for their leaving to Paris. In this extract she used negative politeness intending to minimize threatening his face using "you know". In the extract " No. Just let me stand here a second." She uses directive speech act when she requested him to leave her alone trying to give herself some times to relax and think how she can change her husband mind by questing him to leave her standing by the sea. she used negative politeness trying to reduce his threatening face by using "just" In the extract" What are you doing? Why are we stopping?" she used directive speech act asking her husband Frank why is he stopping the car in the middle of the road in his trying to convince her to accept his idea but she refuses. she used bald on record trying to attract his attention to the urgent situation which was sudden stopping the car refusing his idea of staying in the current city. In her trying

of making him accept her desire, she used expressive speech act as in the extract "How kind of you. How terribly, terribly kind of you" and positive politeness trying to avoid his disagreement. In the extract "Enough to live on for six months without you earning another dime. And with the money we could get from the house and the car, longer", she used representative speech act presenting the fact that contribute in her changing his mind and bald on record politeness using the word "enough" neglecting tacking care of his face.

Quantitatively, Table 8 clarifies that April used directive speech act in her normal argument more other types since the percentages are 60,20 ,20 % respectively. This due to that April tried to open new ways of discussing and finding different ways of changing the current situation. That refers to her trying to create new style of life better than just taking care of children and doing the chores of the house. That indicates she desires to be a beneficial member in the society through working outside the house. She suggested to travel to Paris because She aims to be an actress. It is also clear that she used negative politeness and bald on record politeness more than positive politeness since the percentages are 40,40,20 %. This refers that she tries to vary her ways of discussion intending to affect his insistence on staying in the current city.

Table 9. The Verbal Abuse Techniques and Impoliteness Categories Used by Nick

The extract of the third character (Nick)	The abusive technique	Impoliteness category
1- get out or I will get you out myself	Abusive anger	Negative politeness
2- I don't want this jerk putting his hands on you again	Name calling	Positive politeness
3Have you lost your mind?	Abusive anger	Negative politeness
4- stop messing with my head.	ordering	Negative politeness
5- to show how twisted you are?	Judging and criticizing	Positive politeness

Table 10. The Verbal Frequencies and Percentages of Verbal Abuse Techniques and Impoliteness Categories Used by Nick

Abusive technique	frequency	percentage	Impoliteness category	frequency	percentage
Abusive anger	2	40%	Negative impoliteness	3	%60
Judging and criticizing	1	20%	Positive politeness	2	40%
ordering	1	20%			
Name calling	1	20%			

Qualitatively, Nick used abusive anger and negative politeness in the following extracts: "get out or I will get you out myself " and " Have you lost your mind?" in these extracts he intended to insult Noah when he ordered her to get out his car when she blamed him mentioning his mother left him acting in such a bad behavior, through using "get out ", "I will get you out". He also tried to belittle her abilities of win and prove her capabilities through using "lost your mind" in the second extract when she entered a car race with one of the bad guys that he usually competes with. in the extract " stop messing with my head." he used ordering and negative impoliteness as an illustration that he tried to order her enforcing her to accept his love and mutual him with love when her saw one of the bag guys kissed her. when he kicks him tried to keep her for him only confessing of his love to her. she tried to defend upon him and refused his love claiming that he is a violent person like her father. in the extract "I don't want this jerk putting his hands on you again"" to show how twisted you are?" he used name calling and positive and impoliteness to disorder the picture oof the person who kissed Noah describing him using bad adjectives like "jerk" as a way of his control on her and preventing her from choosing and decide the person she like and live with. In the extract "to show how twisted you are?" Nick gave his opinion about the personality of Noah making her to see her weakness and deny her ability to decide and control the man. he used the word "twisted " trying to threaten her positive face by describing her that she is unable to be free from him as a girl in that society and decide an independent decision. this is a way of making her to love him and practice his control over her as a man of fifties.

Quantitatively, Nick used abusive anger as a verbal abuse technique more than the other types since their percentages are 40, 20,20,20 % respectively. This leads to understand that Nick tried to control over Noah and make her love through using the anger. He also used negative politeness more than positive politeness since the percentages are 60% and 40% respectively. This is a sign that he acts as a man of fifties who control over everything even his beloved through anger and restricting the freedom of the other gender from taking any decision and refusing his idea. He believes that he is more rational person than the other gender. Like Lilvakavivlu (2023) claimed, this is also a reaction to neglecting of his mother when he was a child. when he grew up, he enrolled with bad people and racing. when he met Noah as his stepsister, he tried to practice his masculinity over her.

Table 11. The Speech Act and Politeness Categories Used by Nick

The extract of Nick	The normal argument	Impoliteness category
1- Those turns are impossible	representative	Positive politeness
2- you cannot sneak into this	representative	Bald on record
3- that guy has no blood in his vein	representative	Off record
4-Do you want to spend more time with me?	directive	Negative politeness
5- I'm not going to stand by and do nothing	commissive	Bald on record

Table 12. The Frequencies and Percentages of Speech Act and Politeness Categories Used by Nick

Speech act category	frequency	percentage	Politeness category	frequency	percentage
representative	3	60%	Bald on record	2	40%
Directive	1	20%	Negative politeness	1	20%
commissive	1	20%	Positive politeness	1	20%
			off record	1	20%

Qualitatively, Nick used representative speech act and positive politeness in his normal argument in the extract "Those turns are impossible". he gave his opinion about the turns of cars in one of the scenes when he and Noah were watching TV in that scene Noah was watching and following moving of cars on TV. He entered the room and said that turns of cars are not real. He used "impossible as a sign to positive politeness. In the extract and "you cannot sneak into this", he claims that she wouldn't enter a car race again. he means that he prevented and enforced her from car racing with the guys. He also used representative speech act in the extract " that guy has no blood in his vein " intending to claim that the guy who tried to attract her love he has cold feeling and doesn't have love toward her like his love in this extract ,he used off record politeness intending to deliver a message that he loves her more than anyone else .in the extract , " Do you want to spend more time with me?" he used directive speech act since he asked her about her opinion about him .at the same time he used negative politeness as a sign for his intention to leave a space for her freedom to choose the person she likes to live with and to be her life partner . in the last extract, " I'm not going to stand by and do nothing" he promised to save Noah when her father kidnaped her. He used bald on record intending to confess his desire of Noah and strong love to her.

Quantitatively, Nick used representative speech act as a way of discussing normally more than other types since their percentages are: 60,20,20 % respectively. this due to that tried to present his personal opinion to attract the listener that is represented mostly by Noah. He also used positive politeness more than negative politeness, bald on record and off record since the percentages are 40 ,20,20,20,20% respectively this indicates that he deals with the different issues by using positive adjectives without restricting the desire of the listener for being accepted .in other words. He tried to give his opinion in different scenes without imposing that opinion on the listener that is represented mostly with step sister, Noah.

Table 13. The Verbal Abuse Techniques and Impoliteness Categories Used by Noah

The extract of the fourth character (Noah)	The abusive technique	Impoliteness category
1-Your limited vocabulary doesn't include the word "unisex"	Judging and criticizing	Positive impoliteness
2- why don't you take a picture?	trivializing	Negative impoliteness
3- You wouldn't dare	Judging and criticizing	Bald on record
4- you are not even going to dive me a safety vest	Judging and criticizing	Positive impoliteness
5- God damn. fuck	Abusive anger	Positive politeness

Table 14. The Frequencies and Percentages of Verbal Abuse Techniques and Impoliteness Categories Used by Noah

Abusive technique	frequency	percentage	Impoliteness	Frequency	frequency
Judging and criticizing	3	60%	Positive impoliteness	3	60%
trivializing	1	20%	Negative impoliteness	1	20%
Abusive anger	1	20%	Bald on record	1	20%

Qualitatively, Noah used judging and criticizing and positive impoliteness in the extracts "Your limited vocabulary doesn't include the word "unisex" and " you are not even going to dive me a safety vest". in the first one, she tried to criticize his personality through belittling his knowledge and culture that is unequal to hers. In the second one, she criticized his personality through describing his violence and being another version of her father. In the extract" You wouldn't dare" she also criticized his ability of dismissing her out of his car when they were going to a party. In this time, she criticized him directly without any remedy to his feelings. in the extract, " why don't you take a picture?", she tried to trivialize his looking's through positive impoliteness including ridiculing that looking and surprising of her appearance. In the last extract," God damn. Fuck "she used abusive anger when he left her alone in the middle of the road when she blamed him of his mother's love to him. This done through using taboo word "damn" and "fuck"

Quantitatively, Noah used judging and criticizing as a way of verbal abuse more than trivializing and abusive anger since their percentages are 60,20,20 % respectively. This shows that Noah tried to give a judge on the current situation this is a reaction to her bad past whose source is her abusive father. Rudra (2025) revealed her father was a bad man. he tried to kill her in spite of he taught her to be a good car racer. That leads to inter the jail and made her mother to love and merry another man who is William Leiser. that situation enforced Noah to leave her simple life with her best friends and come to life a different lifestyle. She also used positive politeness more than negative politeness and bald on record since their percentages are 60,20,20 % respectively. this indicates that in order to criticize the current situation because she was Enforced to leave her past city to go and live with her mother and step mother in another city. she criticized this situation by belittling every side of it. one of these sides, her step brother nick for being violent and enforce her to do everything like leaving car racing and love him. this remind her of her bad past with the violent father who was treating her mother badly. She tried to reject this situation through criticizing using either taboo word or inappropriate identity markers.

Table 15. The Speech Act and Politeness Categories Used by Noah

The extract of Noah	The normal argument	Politeness category
1- why would it be	directive	Bald on record
2- What do you mean?	directive	Bald on record
3- Where were you?	directive	Bald on record
4- I think I was your only sister	representative	Positive politeness
5- I'm sorry.	expressive	Positive politeness

Table 16. The Frequencies and Percentages of Speech Act and Politeness Categories Used by Noah

Speech act category	frequency	percentage	Politeness category	frequency	percentage
Directive	3	60%	Bald on record	3	60%
Representative	1	20%	Positive politeness	2	40%

Qualitatively, in her normal argument, Noah used directive speech act and bald on record politeness in the first three extracts, " why would it be?", " what do you mean?" and " Where were you?". In the first one, she refused the idea of her step father when he told her to take his surname as her surname. she used the form of directive speech act with little care to his feelings. In the second one, she tried to understand the nature she entered recently. she asked Mario for clarification when he told her that Nick is not going to work as he told his father and stepmother but to a party. she tried to adapt into such a fake environment. .in the third one ,she tried to be near to him as a part of her adaptation in the new environment .she asked him where has he been when he entered the living room she was watching a car racing using the direct way without any maintain to the feeling and the face of the listener.in the extract"- I think I was your only sister "she used representative speech act intending to illustrate that she is the only girl he loves . she also used positive politeness by the word "think" means that she avoids disagreement and deliver a message that she also loves him through asking direct questions. In the last extract "I'm sorry" she expresses her sorry toward her refusion of her mother's idea for living with her stepfather since she saw a comfortable house with independent room with all comfort tools and her needs. In this way she used expressive speech act through avoiding disagreement.

Quantitatively, Noah used directive speech act as a way of discussing normally more than representative and expressive since their percentages are 60,20,20 respectively. This due to her desire to open a new way of discussing far from her suffering of enforcement. In this way she tried to find something enable her to adapt with the new situation. she also tried to adapt with the ideas of the new people that she will live with mostly especially Nick. she also used bald on record politeness more than positive politeness since their percentages are 60 and 40 respectively. This means that she doesn't care about the feelings of the listener. This is due to her previous environment that she was living with her father when she was violated and he was teaching car racing. she is borrough up in an environment full of violence and enforcement .no place in her past environment for discussing smoothly and treating her as a person with volition to take her decision like the skill she would like to improve.

Table 17. The Frequencies and Percentages of Verbal Abuse Techniques with Impoliteness Categories and Speech Act with Politeness Categories Used by Frank, April, Nick and Noah

The character	Abusive language	impoliteness category	Normal language	politeness category
Frank	Name-calling	Positive impoliteness	representative	Negative politeness
	2 40%	4 80%	2 40%	2 40%
April	Judging and criticizing	Bald on record	directive	Bald on record
	3 60%	2 40%	3 60%	2 40%
Nick	Abusive anger	Negative impoliteness	representative	Bald on record
	2 40%	3 60%	3 60%	2 40%
Noah	Judging and criticizing	Positive impoliteness	directive	Bald on record
	3 60%	3 60%	6 60%	3 60%

Table above shows that the men used name-calling and abusive anger mostly. This is justified as the men in their nature and physiological state try to control over women regardless to the way they use. In other words ,they don't try to reflect a good picture to the others .That is why they usually try to cover their weaknesses and rejected ideas as well as practicing masculine power through belittling the women by shouting ,calling names and even describe them with bad adjectives .On the contrary, women use judging

and criticizing mostly .This is justified as the women reject the current situation and try to change it with a wisdom .This means that they criticize that situation and try to create ways to change that situation .the mentality of men in dealing with matters differs from women's. This result is similar to what Pradhan (2023) figured out when he concluded that the gender identity is constructed socially and the physiological nature of the Women Compared to men, are mature more rapidly and live longer that makes her judge the surrounding environment. He adds that the traits of masculinity are most closely associated with aggressive behavior and obscenity. From the side of impoliteness, it is clear that men use positive impoliteness and negative impoliteness. This means that they threat the both faces of the listener especially the women when they intend to defend their ideas and prevent them from doing a certain thing. The women use bald on record and positive impoliteness. This means that the women usually direct in their discussion. in other words, women don't use negative politeness that refers to they intend little or no threat to the face of the listener and if they used threat they do not impose something on them but they to convince them logically. This is due to the nature of the man who practices his masculinity in deciding without any trying to conviction while the women according to her nature she is more wisdom. she takes a decision with evidences and tries to convince the listener using the logical evidences. This agrees with Suhandoko, Unlyatin,Riesti and Ningrum (2021) when they found out that men use positive impoliteness while women use negative politeness as a way of their negotiation.

In the normal discussion, it is clear that the nature of the men makes them use representative speech act since they try to present facts which are visual only by them. the women use directive speech act since they try to hear ideas and open ways of discussion before take her decision to be a wisdom decision. This result agrees with what Subon (2013) found out when he concluded that men use affirmatives while women use questions in their normal negotiations. Both genders use the same ways of politeness which are negative politeness and bald on record. That mean both of try to reach to the purpose of the discussion with taking care of the freedom of the of the listener. This result agrees with the study that is done by Muhammad and Diannurdianti (2023) who find out that male and female used bald on record politeness in their discussion.

Conclusion

The amazing of God's creating the universe appears in the difference between the two genders to balance that universe. This study proves this difference through analyzing the mentality of both. Men differ from women in dealing with the current situation. Both of them have desire to change the current situation if it is miserable but in different ways. On one hand, the men use his physical power to control over the women even the women are smarter in dealing with this situation. They try to in force themselves accept their life as it is even if they hope to change it. On the other hand, the women use her creativity to change the unacceptable situation despite of her limited physical power. The researchers answer the questions of this study:

- 1-The men used representative speech act with while bald on record politeness and negative impoliteness while the women used directive speech act with bald on record politeness
- 2- The men used name- calling and abusive anger as verbal abuse technique with positive and negative impoliteness while the women used judging and criticizing with bald on record and positive impoliteness.

References

Austin, J. L. (1962). *How to do things with words: The William James lectures delivered at Harvard University in 1955*. Oxford, England: Oxford University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/acprof:oso/9780198245537.001.0001>

- Basta, G. (2020). Revolutionary Road, review and analysis of a masterpiece. *Medium*. Retrieved from <https://giovannibasta.medium.com/revolutionary-road-review-and-analysis-of-a-masterpiece-c1f9d9128838>
- Battistella, E. L. (2005). *Bad language: Are some words better than others?* Oxford, England: Oxford University Press.
- Bousfield, D. (2008). *Impoliteness in struggle for power*. Berlin, Germany: Mouton de Gruyter.
- Brown, P., & Levinson, S. (1978). Universals in language usage: Politeness phenomena. In E. Goody (Ed.), *Questions and politeness: Strategies in social interaction* (pp. 15-26). Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
- Brown, P., & Levinson, S. C. (1987). *Politeness: Some universals in language usage*. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
- Butler, J. (1997). *Excitable speech: A politics of the performative*. New York, NY: Routledge.
- Culpeper, J. (1996). Towards an anatomy of impoliteness. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 25(3), 349-367. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-2166\(95\)00014-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0378-2166(95)00014-6)
- Diani, I., Arono, & Yunita. (2022). A pragmatics study on verbal abuse against women and children by Bengkulu communities on social media, at schools, and in families. *KEMBARA: Journal Keilmuan Bahasa, Sastra, dan Pengajarannya*, 8(2). <https://doi.org/10.22219/kembara.v8i2.21900>
- Evans, P. (2009). *The Verbally Abusive Relationship* (3rd ed., pp. 81-100). Adams Media.
- Gottman, J. M., & Silver, N. (1999). *The seven principles for making marriage work*. New York, NY: Crown Publishing Group.
- Hitchcock, D. (2007). Informal logic and the concept of argument. In D. Jacquette (Ed.), *Philosophy of logic* (pp. 101–129). Amsterdam, Netherlands: Elsevier.
- Klein, H., & Shiffman, K. S. (2012). Verbal aggression in animated cartoons. *International Journal of Child and Adolescent Health*, 5(1), 7-12. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/235989511_Verbal_Aggression_in_Animated_Cartoons#full-text
- Lilvakavivlu. (2023, August 28). Movie review: *My fault*. Retrieved from <https://lilvakavivlu.wordpress.com/2023/08/28/movie-review-my-fault/>
- Martency, J. (n.d.). Arguing using critical thinking. Retrieved from [https://socialsci.libretxts.org/Bookshelves/Communication/Argument_and_Debate/Arguing_Using_Critical_Thinking_\(Martency\)/08%3A_Validity_Or_Truth/8.04/](https://socialsci.libretxts.org/Bookshelves/Communication/Argument_and_Debate/Arguing_Using_Critical_Thinking_(Martency)/08%3A_Validity_Or_Truth/8.04/)
- Muhammad, A., & Diannurdianti, A. (2023). The use of politeness strategies based on gender differences in *Harry Potter and the Prisoner of Azkaban* movie: A socio-pragmatic study. *Jurnal Bahasa Inggris Terapan*, 9(2). Retrieved from <https://jurnal.polban.ac.id/inggris/article/download/5736/3539>
- Mullany, L., & Stockwell, P. (2010). *Introducing English language: A resource book for students*. Nottingham, England: Routledge.
- O'Driscoll, J. (2020). *Offensive language: Taboo, offence, and social control*. London, England: Bloomsbury Academic.
- Pradhan, K. (2023). The impact of language on gender. *Bhairavi*, 22(5). Retrieved from <https://www.jvwu.ac.in/uploads/News/Document/ccebfb0da-f9c8-4d86-9b2d-7dfbbf6feeb0.pdf>
- Schwartzman, L. H. (2002). Hate speech, illocution and social context: A critique of Judith Butler. *Journal of Social Philosophy*, 33(3), 421–441. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-9833.00287>
- Searle, J. (1969). *Speech acts: An essay in the philosophy of language*. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.

- Searle, J. R. (1985). *Expression and meaning: Studies in the theory of speech acts*. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
- Shadows of Control. (2024). *Words that wound: Distinguishing verbal abuse from normal arguments*. Retrieved from <https://shadowsofcontrol.com/articles/distinguishing-verbal-abuse-from-normal-arguments>
- Stollznow, K. (2020). *On the offensive: Prejudice in language past and present*. Cambridge, England: Cambridge University Press.
- Subon, F. (2013). Gender differences in the use of linguistic forms in the speech of men and women in the Malaysian context. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science*, 13(3). Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/87721581/Gender_Differences_in_the_Use_of_Linguistic_Forms_in_the_Speech_of_Men_and_Women_in_the_Malaysian_Context#loswp-work-container
- Suhandoko, D., Ariyanti, L., & Fitriana, E. (2021). Impoliteness and gender differences in *The Edge of Seventeen* movie. *Journal of Literature and Language Teaching*, 12(2), 228-242. <https://doi.org/10.15642/NOBEL.2021.12.2.228-242>
- Tartory, R., Ali, A. M., & Khattab, A. (2022). Critical discourse analysis of verbal violence in William Shakespeare's *Merchant of Venice*. *Theory and Practice in Language Studies*, 12(9), 1870-1878. <https://doi.org/10.17507/tpls.1209.24>
- Thielemann, N., & Kosta, P. (Eds.). (2013). *Approaches to Slavic interaction*. Amsterdam, Netherlands: John Benjamins Publishing Company.
- Walaszewska, E., & Piskorska, A. (Eds.). (2012). *Relevance theory: More than understanding*. Newcastle, England: Cambridge Scholars Publishing.
- Wierzbicka, A. (1987). *English speech act verbs: A semantic dictionary*. Sydney, Australia: Academic Press.
- Yousif, N. A. (2023). Socio-pragmatic study of insulting in English news. *Journal of Almustadama Studies*, 4(2). Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/378821013_A_Socio-Pragmatic_Study_of_Insulting_in_English_News

